

Entrepreneurial Action

MOD007666

Action Research Thesis

An Implementation of Fuel Theft Prevention System; An Entrepreneurial Approach

Student ID: 2153176

Anglia Ruskin University

MBA

Word count: 12469

Date: 5 August 2022

Contents

Introduction	3
Methods of Fuel Theft	4
Fuel Theft Prevention System	5
Background	8
Research Questions, Aims & Objectives	10
Research Question	10
Literature Review	11
Research Design & Methodology	17
Research Design	17
Philosophical Interpretivism	18
Inductive Methodology	19
Qualitative Research	19
Experimental Investigation	20
The Study's Limitations	20
Synopsis	20
Research Gantt Chart	21
Thematic Model	22
The Study's Limitations	22
Fuel Theft Model	22
A. Fuel value extraction	25
B. Purity extraction	26
C. Application Wireframes	27
.....	27
Analysis	29
Discussion	34
Entrepreneurial Competencies	37
Execution Strategy	38
An Examination Of The Development Of Entrepreneurial Approach	39
Conclusion	41
References	45

Introduction

Fuel-efficient vehicles have always been the primary choice of any frequent fuel consumer. Such vehicles run on quality octane fuel to give consumers better mileage with low emissions and are less hazardous to the environment. With the hike of supply/demand on the crude fuel prices, vehicle fuel consumers face fuel theft with low octane quality from fuel pumping stations, which is impossible to perceive through vehicle built-in fuel gauges.

The world has gone digital, allowing us to work with real-time systems effortlessly. Simultaneously, a new vehicle framework carried out an advanced fuel meter. In any case, the actual fuel present in the fuel tank of the vehicle was not displayed with regards to digits but instead as far as a bar or a redirecting needle, so we had no clue about the available fuel present in the fuel tank of the vehicle; it just showed the degree of fuel present in the fuel tank. To resolve this issue, we made an advanced fuel meter framework that showcases fuel esteem in digits and fuel robbery esteem in digits, for example, 1lit, 1.5lits, 2lits, and so on. The computerized fuel meter fits the present vehicle fuel tank integrated with a smartphone application. Our undertaking might incorporate data, for example, the distance went by a vehicle inside a specific amount of fuel, permitting us to work out vehicle execution as far as millage.

In some cases, clients fill fuel as far as petroleum from a petroleum filling siphon; they fill the petroleum carefully; nonetheless, in most vehicles, there is no computerized framework; all things being equal, there is a bar or avoidance needle framework, which doesn't give the exact fuel-filled by the consumer; accordingly, the petroleum filling theft is undermined, and the consumer knows nothing about the cheating because of the conventional framework since fuel might be less or more than the filled worth. All benefit goes to the gas filling station owner, who frequently dupes consumers. All vehicles have a bar or avoiding pointer estimating framework, so

they don't have the foggiest idea about the exact amount of fuel entered into the vehicle, permitting the gas station proprietor to dupe the customer. In this way, the idea of a computerized fuel meter is reasonable for fuel signs and fuel burglary and for keeping clients from being tricked by petroleum filling station proprietors. The current research has been designed to deliver the whole eco-system based on an innovative phone application on the software portion and the Single board computer-based circuitry with leveling sensors and radio-based system on the hardware portion. An innovative phone application will provide statistical data of past and current liquid fuel consumption according to mileage, future predictions according to the current liquid fuel level, and how much mileage can be covered according to the average obtained by previous data, following the nearest fueling station indication, and alerts on low fuel levels with purity meter of liquid fuel using octane. The system will also generate a notification during fuel filling.

Methods of Fuel Theft

There are several methods for stealing fuel. Unfortunately, some approaches are effortless and straightforward to implement. Hand-operated or automated siphons decant fuel into portable containers that may be swiftly put into a criminal vehicle or transported off-site by hand. Fuel has been poured directly into tanks placed on trucks in more complex illicit operations, enabling more significant fuel volumes to be raised faster. Fuel theft not only causes financial hardship for the victim since they must pay to replace the stolen fuel, but it may also cause significant physical damage to equipment that must be repaired. Supply lines may be cut, sight gauges can be shattered, and fuel can seep into the surrounding area, leading to expensive clean-ups and voiding insurance. Because of the nature of the crime, determining who is stealing fuel may be difficult. It might be an opportunist capitalizing on a company's poor fuel management. Unfortunately, theft may frequently occur from inside the organization. While most of your workers will be honest, diligent

individuals, it is an unpleasant reality that some employees will not be. Fuel is a valuable resource; for example, an unhappy driver dissatisfied with his working circumstances may be motivated to take advantage of the easily accessible fuel for personal use or benefit. Internal fuel theft might cause a breach of confidence. You must take actions to avoid and eliminate fuel theft inside your organization, such as training your drivers and providing them with safe and fair working conditions. We suggest investing in a fuel management system, such as those offered by Fuel stations, for complete peace of mind and the ability to check your fuel levels actively and correctly.

Fuel Theft Prevention System

Once the fuel management system has been implemented at your depot, you may fill your tanks using the monitored pumps. Using the online fuel management software, the fuel management system prevents illegal access, monitors throughputs, and fuel waste, and generates reports. These reports' data may be utilized to decrease waste and prevent fuel theft. To monitor your fuel supply levels, we suggest supplementing the Fuel management system with a fuel monitoring system such as a Tank watch. The cutting-edge technology includes alarms and notifications that may be activated if there are any odd stock movements, such as if the fuel levels in the tank are lowering yet the pump attached to the tank is not working. A fuel management system is the most precise approach to keeping track of your fuel supplies. If you become a victim of fuel theft, the system will give you the information you need to determine whether the discrepancy originated inside your firm or from an opportunist. From an economic standpoint, all internal combustion engines that rely on liquid fuel must be very fuel efficient. All of these engines have the most modern automatic fuel indicator systems. These are gadgets that are incorporated into the system. At the user level, there should be some mechanism for knowing the amount of fuel at all times.

The safety and security of fuel are critical. In recent years, rising oil consumption has resulted in rising fuel prices. Many firms, particularly big car fleets, may see their overheads rise. Global oil production and demand predictions for the future have lately altered dramatically. Still, these adjustments have mostly canceled each other out: the view remains one of a relatively balanced market. Forecasting, however, becomes most challenging during periods of rapid market change. Before crude prices plummeted earlier, predictions from the International Energy Agency, the US Energy Information Administration, and OPEC predicted that global oil consumption would climb by around 1.35 million b/d in the future, with a very tiny positive global supply/demand balance.

The VFTD is a vehicle fuel detection system that is hardware and software-based, practical, cost-effective, and enables remote fuel-level monitoring to meet the demands of fuel savings owing to one of the few concerns mentioned above. Work was completed utilizing an embedded control-based system for remote fuel level monitoring. The researcher investigated fuel monitoring and vehicle tracking systems using a single board computer as a control system with an integrated smartphone application. The researcher used third-party monitoring software to identify fuel theft and vehicle location. The system includes an ultrasonic fuel sensor, a numeric lock, and third-party monitoring software to detect fuel theft. The work of writers is extensive, and just a handful are listed here. This effort will assist in providing periodic data regarding fuel level and vehicle location and tracking fuel theft. The present study is intended to function using a single board computer and integrated smartphone technologies. This technique gathers satellite coordinates as well as other crucial information. When an attacker attempts to obtain unlawful entry to the car, it sends a notification. Since the smartphone is one of the most famous and broadly utilized methods of versatile correspondence, it is doable and exciting. Different frameworks and applications might

be made to work with this area because it is used, carried out, and adhered to worldwide guidelines. The framework depends on a single board computer and incorporates a smartphone application as an overall framework for versatile correspondence. This venture utilizes the current vehicle system, and fuel level sensors are installed on the vehicle fuel tanks, and two-way correspondence is achieved using a smartphone application. The task incorporates planning and building a remote fuel-level sensor and observing the fuel level. Notifications are sent from vehicle fuel tank sensors to the smartphone application.

One more fundamental component of this study is utilizing passwords to lock the vehicle. During an attack, the alarm could likewise be actuated. This fuel-level observing framework will ensure that fuel is utilized effectively, that functional expenses are kept to a base, and that benefit is boosted. This innovation is easy to utilize, simple to introduce, and economical. Assume your vehicle's overall fuel utilization is unreasonable. It may be because of different elements, remembering vehicles needing a fix. These drivers are not rehearsing eco-driving or safe driving, regardless of whether you suspect it, drivers, who are taking fuel. Assuming a vehicle's fuel utilization is decisively deteriorating, it is a warning that something isn't right and should be checked. Assuming you know about the accompanying fuel burglary strategies, you might be searching for an answer that can help you recognize and take out this extortion. The following are four methods of fuel burglary that might affect armadas; this approach is standard in associations that use manually written logbooks to screen fuel buys and utilize or have a swelled use rate, which might make it much less complex for representatives to take fuel. Fuel might be placed into different vehicles for this situation; drivers can exploit the misjudgment or estimate the utilization procedure. The primary thing that triggers a notification: albeit not precisely like older style siphoning, is that fuel might be siphoned out of the tank. At the same time, if the vehicle is inactive

(the vehicle can then be monitored secretly), or even by utilizing a sensor motion device that can calculate fuel economy per the kilometers/miles traveled.

In certain conditions, a massive amount of fuel enters the vehicle tank, while the rest is filled in a holder or another vehicle. It might appear easy to identify; however, assuming it is done in small amounts, you may not take note. You can uncover these methodologies assuming you have the suitable apparatuses. Assuming that you keep utilizing manual strategies to screen your fuel use or rely upon fuel bills to follow fuel use, you might burn through a truckload of cash without knowing where the fuel goes. It contains a coordinated fuel the board module that might show constant buys and related worries. You can likewise depend on driving observing alarms to decide whether your group is driving really, an upkeep module to guarantee vehicles are kept up with roadworthy, and you can set fuel utilization goals for your vehicle. Assuming you are worried about fuel burglary, there is a simple response.

Background

Fuel is one of the most critical wares on earth, which has brought about a massive expansion in fuel robbery worldwide. Most of the fuel is taken while being shipped between businesses. As a result of the numerous calculated intricacies included, distinguishing this burglary becomes extreme. A protected technique is proposed to keep gas burglary from the big hauler. The gadget consistently screens the fuel level in the big hauler's stockpiling tank. When the fuel level falls under a foreordained level, an alarm is shipped off the driver and the fuel organization. The primary level of assurance is a keypad security framework because of double-secret phrase confirmation. A GPS module lets specialists follow the truck's situation through a portable application.

The proposed framework's curiosity is an IoT (Internet of Things) empowered security framework that will guarantee correspondence between the source and collector parties, and after affirmation, fuel will be administered. This system will play an important role in preventing fuel theft. Fuel-efficient cars have always been the first choice of any frequent fuel consumer. Such vehicles operate on high-octane fuel to provide the customer with higher mileage while emitting low emissions that are less harmful to the environment. With the increase in supply/demand on crude fuel prices, vehicle fuel customers risk fuel theft from fuel pumping stations with poor octane quality, which is hard to detect using vehicle built-in fuel gauges. The technology in this research tends to digitally read the quantity of fuel in the tank, i.e., 1.0 liters, 1.5 liters, 2.0 liters, and so on.

Furthermore, fuel theft is a real-world problem that must be addressed. In the proposal, if fuel is taken, it triggers a notification sent to the integrated mobile phone application. Furthermore, fuel theft is also measuring the vehicle fuel quality as per the octane level using vehicle emission sensors. A research project focuses on developing a digital display of the particular fuel quantity in tanks and assisting in the verification of the amount of fuel injected into the fuel tank. Finally, the fuel is filled in two levels, and the system sends a notification to the vehicle owner, indicating the amount, quantity, date, time, and so on. There is also the vehicle's specific location. The research was focused on consumer fuel theft. Almost all vehicles are powered by increasingly costly fuel. Most vehicles have a simple fuel delivery system that is as easy as a touch with the primary/backup choice. This mechanism is vulnerable to theft since anybody may readily steal fuel from the fuel tank. Each fuel tank has a minimum capacity of 30-40 liters, and for motorbikes, it is min 10 liters. A technique to prevent fuel theft was created as part of this research. The system takes advantage of the vehicle's energy supply. The vehicle must be firing to withdraw fuel from the fuel tank. This research aims to prevent vehicle fuel theft using a single board computer and

mobile application technologies. The technology can identify multiple ways of vehicle fuel theft and trigger a notification over the smartphone application. The single board computer is integrated with a GPS module that determines the vehicle's location, which delivers the notification to the smartphone user through the integrated application. The single board computer is integrated with fuel leveling and emission sensors to determine the quantity and quality, respectively, which further communicates and shares the information with a smartphone application.

Research Questions, Aims & Objectives

Research Question

1. How can fuel theft be prevented?
2. How can people monitor my fuel consumption?
3. How do Petrol pump steal fuel?
4. Do people steal fuel?

Research Aims

This research will explore the possible ways of fuel theft and how it can prevent. The purpose of this research is to investigate the prevention system. The research has been designed to deliver the whole eco-system based on a smart phone application on the software portion and the Single board computer-based circuitry with leveling sensors and radio-based system on the hardware portion. Smart phone application will be providing statistical data of past and current liquid fuel consumption according to mileage, future predictions according to the current liquid fuel level and how much mileage can be covered according to the average obtained by previous data, next nearest fueling station indication, and alerts on low fuel levels with purity meter of liquid fuel using octane. The system will also generate a notification during fuel filling.

Literature Review

All internal combustion engines running on gas fuel have to be very fuel efficient from an economic point of view. All these engines are equipped with the most advanced automated fuel indication devices/sensors, and such systems are built-in devices. There should be some provision at the user level to know the quantity of fuel and monitoring during filling at all times. The safety and security of fuel are of utmost importance. Although the literature covers a wide variety of such theories, this review will focus on major themes which repeatedly emerge throughout the literature review. These themes are the incorporation of the self-concept into traditional theories of theft, the influence of theft, and the increasing importance of security and control. This research will focus on fuel theft and the most liable way to mitigate such vulnerabilities.

This section reviews the literature that any type of fuel is a volatile compound that is colorless, odorless, and tasteless. So, when these compounds spread in the air, it will be difficult to identify with the naked human eye. At present several methods are available which detect Fuel leakage but the drawback of these systems is it uses a static network of sensors. This research noticed that the correct source of leakage could not be identified by using this static network. The fuel will spread very fast in the air. as soon as it leaks. Thus, a proper device should be required to detect the leakage. In this project, an embedded electronic platform is used which can monitor a moving vehicle with a chemical sensing system for Fuel leakage detection and environment monitoring (Ganesh Katkar, ShivamLanke, "Fuel Checker and --Theft Indication"- 2017) [2]. However, a closer look at the literature on the proposed method reveals several gaps and shortcomings regarding the sensors being used to detect anomalies because the device suggested is not calibrated as per the standards because plausible deviations might occur.

The authors bring some information about the background of the problem on vehicle tracking systems that can be used for fleet management, asset tracking, surveillance, stolen vehicle recovery, and many more [6]. Advances in modern technologies like ubiquitous computing, the Internet of Things (IoT), and the availability of economical hardware building blocks are creating a new wave of vehicular tracking systems. In this work, the author presents VERTIGO, a GPS, GSM, and GPRS technology-based vehicular tracking system that is accurate, robust, flexible, economical, and feature-rich. Unlike the traditional COTS (Commercial of The Shelf) vehicular tracking system, which is closed and confined to smartphones and PCs, the research explains that vehicular tracking system infrastructure is open sourced and is available for the research fraternity to test experiment and add more features. (Manihatty Bojan, "Designing Vehicle Tracking System – An Open Source Approach") - 2014 [6]. Several questions regarding the monitoring system reliability remain to be addressed that focus more on the security and reliability of the surveillance for the stolen vehicles is uncertain, which means that such systems are vulnerable.

The project employed a fuel theft detection methodology that prescribes creating a digital display of the exact amount of fuel contained in the vehicle's tank and also helps cross-check the quantity of fuel filled at the petrol bunk. Finally, once the fuel is filled at a bunk, the device also sends an SMS to the vehicle owner indicating the amount, quantity, date, time, etc. And also gives the exact location of the vehicle (Mrs.Udayavalli.V..... "Embedded System Based Intelligent Digital Fuel Gauge"- 2014) [3]. Some key questions and notions are still not discussed in the literature, i.e., the calibration of sensors/devices, which is crucial in detecting anomalies.

This study reflects on Motorcycles fuel theft. Mostly all motorcycles are petrol driven whose costs have been increasing steadily. The motorcycles come with a simple fuel delivery mechanism, which is nothing but a simple tap with a main/reserve option. This system is

susceptible to pilferage, and anyone can remove petrol from the fuel tank without trouble. Each petrol tank has a capacity of at least 10 Liters. A mechanism has been developed to prevent this fuel theft in this project. The mechanism uses a power supply from the vehicle. So for the fuel to come out of the fuel tank, the vehicle must be in ON condition (Mr. Ravindra "Analysis and Design -Of Fuel Theft Prevention And Automation"- 2016) [4]. A further question is whether the such methodology is reliable for vehicle fuel mechanisms.

As previously reported in the literature, this research implements theft prevention in motorcycles using GSM, GPS, and Android technology, demonstrating a system that can track, monitor, and stop the stolen motorcycle. The GPS module sends the motorcycle position to the microcontroller, which then sends the message to the user's smartphone through the GSM module. Here Atmel microcontroller, air solenoid, and water solenoid valves are interfaced with the GSM modem and GPS module, which will be fixed in the motorcycle. Users can stop the vehicle from being theft by the android application (Shanmuganathan System for Two Wheeler Using Android"- 2015) [5]. Several similar methods are reported in the literature to address this issue, but the calibration of devices is still not suggested.

The relatively new research perspective was a GSM-based Vehicle Fuel Theft Detection System with SMS indication has application in cars, Bikes, and all other vehicles. This project has a GSM modem that sends SMS to vehicle owners when fuel theft occurs. Vehicle Petrol theft is one of the main concerns of many bike owners and car owners. Many times, we have heard, or some of us have already faced that petrol from their bike or cars has been stolen. The main intention of this project is to avoid such a situation. In the SMS-based petrol theft detection system, we have used a Level sensor to detect the petrol level in the petrol tank. If the level goes below a certain threshold level, this sensor gives the microcontroller a particular signal. Then microcontroller turns

on the buzzer and sends an SMS to the car/bike owner. The microcontroller is the system's main heart or Central Processing Unit [18].

This study is based on a project focusing on the Vehicle fuel theft problem. It senses the amount of fuel in the tank and visually displays it to the user. It successfully detects fuel thefts-using-a-unique method. It detects whether the vehicle is turned off. If the fuel decreases while the vehicle is turned off, it triggers an event, and this event is linked to message-sending functionality. The fuel level sensing gauge will be connected to μC through ADC. The quantity of the fuel will be displayed on the LCD. A GSM modem with a SIM card will be interfaced with μC . If the fuel level in the tank decreases while the vehicle is in an OFF state, then an alert will be sent to the user's mobile in text form [16].

This research paper proposed a novel data-clustering algorithm based on the mode of the current data to determine the misuse of the fuel of the vehicles. The results reflect that this algorithm could be used to implement an effective check on the misuse of fuel in big organizations [14].

This research paper is focused on a Simple and Hybrid ANN-based approach for anomaly detection. In a simple approach on how Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN), Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Simulated Annealing Neural Network (SA) are used for anomaly detection? While in a hybrid approach, how more than one above technique is used? Further, the research compares the different ANN-based techniques regarding training time, a number of epochs required, converge rate, detection rate, learning approach, etc. [12].

This research is based on Vehicle fuel marking programs comprising several facets, including fuel marking methods, supply chain security, field sampling, and testing, lab testing, and

data analytics. These operational aspects are tightly linked to integrity and program efficiencies [13].

Fig. B

This research study work was carried out with the review of the ARM7LPC2148 processor, the GPS module, and the GSM module – figure B. The power supply for the whole system operates at 3.3V and 5V voltages. The use of an alphanumeric keypad enters the security code. With the support of the GSM module, the GPS module may be used to locate any place and show the location's coordinates. Figure 1 depicts the overall system design. Processor ARM7TDMI (ARM7TDMI): To build new microprocessor-based products and applications fast, embedded systems developers and system-on-chip designers are increasingly choosing individual microprocessor cores as well as a family of tools, libraries, and off-the-shelf components from a variety of vendors, including Intel. ARM is one of the most popular processor architectures accessible to embedded system developers. In recent years, the ARM architecture has emerged as the most widely used 32-bit architecture in the world, with a large range of integrated circuits (ICs) available from various IC vendors. Products using ARM processors range from cell phones and tablets to car braking systems and other electronic devices and systems. The ARM7 microcontroller family is most extensively utilized in embedded system applications. T-D-M-I is an abbreviation for T is an abbreviation for Thumb, which is a 16-bit instruction that is an extension

to the 32-bit ARM architecture that is referred to as the processor's states. D and I are the on-chip debug features available on all ARM cores when combined. These are the Debug signals and the Embedded ICE logic, respectively, on the chip.

M denotes the support for 64-bit results and an upgraded multiplier, both of which increase performance. Recently, this multiplier has become common on all ARMv4 architectures and above. Its LPC2138 microcontrollers, built on an ARM7TDMI-S CPU with real-time emulation and integrated trace support, combine the microcontroller with either 32 kB of embedded high-speed flash memory or 64 kB of embedded high-speed flash memory, depending on the configuration. A 128-bit wide memory interface and a unique accelerator design allow 32-bit code to be executed at the highest possible clock rate. For applications where code size is crucial, the alternative 16-bit Thumb mode cuts code by more than 30% while imposing the smallest possible performance cost. The small size and low power consumption of these microcontrollers make them excellent for applications where downsizing is critical, such as access control and point-of-sale systems. With a wide range of serial communications interfaces and on-chip SRAM options of 8 kB, 16 kB, and 32 kB, they are particularly well suited for communication gateways and protocol converters, soft modems, voice recognition, and low-end imaging applications, as they provide both a large buffer size and high processing power, making them ideal for these applications. These microcontrollers are especially well suited for industrial control and medical applications, thanks to their various 32-bit timers, single or dual 10-bit 8-channel ADC(s), 10-bit DAC, PWM channels, and 47 GPIO lines with up to nine edge or level sensitive external interrupt pins [1].

Research Design & Methodology

According to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016, p. 4), is the "concept of how a research should be done." This study's methodology was based on Figure 1 and the research onion, both of which were derived from Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016, p.124).

Figure 1: Research Onion (Source: Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016,

The study is divided into two phases. After we complete Phase 1, we will go on to Phase 2, which will entail primary research. Here, we'll also discuss the strategy that will be followed in the second phase, which will include primary research.

Research Design

Figure 2 shows the research onion categories that were chosen and explains why they were chosen.

Figure 2: Lean Manufacturing project research onion

Philosophical Interpretivism

Interpretivism, according to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016), embraces human interest and emphasises seeing organisations from the perspectives of multiple groups of people. Employees and management are critical to the success of FTP adoption, making them a key stakeholder in our research.

In value-bound studies, the researcher is an important component of the study object, and their interpretations are critical to the total contribution of the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016, p.136).

Inductive Methodology

Despite the fact that FTP has been in use for decades, its primary use has been in the car industry. There has been much too little study about the effect of FTP on the food processing industry. As a result, we chose an inductive strategy, which, according to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016), aims to generate a hypothesis based on observation. As seen in Figure 17, Goddard and Melville's (2004) extension of this approach attempts to construct a theory by drawing meaning from existing data sets. According to Goddard and Melville, this action research employs an inductive technique (2004).

Induction: A Research Reasoning Method

- ▶ Inductive Research provides an alternative approach to theory.

- ▶ Theory does not guide and influence the collection of data, but rather it is derived from the analysis of the collected data.

- ▶ Inductive reasoning generates broad generalizations from specific observations.

Qualitative Research

Because this research is based on the inductive technique, qualitative data will be employed (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016, p.168). The research will utilise the mono method of data

collecting, as stated by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016, p.168), who indicate that single data collection approaches and accompanying qualitative analysis processes may be employed in mono method qualitative investigations.

Experimental Investigation

Experimental investigation was chosen as the approach for this research because of its focus on problem-solving via the application of many forms of knowledge in a collaborative context (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016, p.189). When applied to certain tasks, augmented reality (AR) may aid in the resolution of problems such as inefficiencies by providing for a fuller grasp of the problem at hand. Both the researcher and the stakeholders desire to discover a solution to the organizational problem at hand, which is the company's operational inefficiencies (Coghlan and Brannick, 2010, p.5). An AR strategy promotes organizational learning by conducting a thorough diagnosis of the issue, developing a plan of action, executing that plan, and evaluating its effectiveness, all of which lead to the development of actionable outcomes and recommendations for addressing the issues and fostering organizational change (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016, pp.190-191). Despite the fact that this study focuses on the use of FTP to improve operational efficiency, the qualitative underpinnings of AR allow for the addition of quantitative factors.

The Study's Limitations

Because many databases providing important information required a membership fee, the researcher was limited to accessing either publicly accessible databases or databases to which the university paid. This has the potential to jeopardise the accuracy and integrity of the data used in this research.

Synopsis

This study relied on secondary sources for data, and its design was created using the research onion and backed by existing literature. This study relied on secondary sources for data,

and its design was created using the research onion and backed by existing literature. was chosen as the approach for this research because of its focus on problem-solving via the application of many forms of knowledge in a collaborative context (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016, p.189). When applied to certain tasks, augmented reality may aid in the resolution of problems such as inefficiencies by providing for a more full grasp of the problem at hand. Both the researcher and the stakeholders desire to discover a solution to the organizational problem at hand, which is the company's operational inefficiencies (Coghlan and Brannick, 2010, p.5). An AR strategy promotes organizational learning by conducting a thorough diagnosis of the issue, developing a plan of action, executing that plan, and evaluating its effectiveness, all of which lead to the development of actionable outcomes and recommendations for addressing the issues and fostering organizational change (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill 2016, pp.190-191). Despite the fact that this study focuses on the use of FTP to improve operational efficiency, the qualitative underpinnings of AR allow for the addition of quantitative factors.

Research Gantt Chart

Cycle	Phase	Start	Finish
0	Groundwork	Dec 2021	Jan 2022
1	Plan	Mar 2022	Mar 2022
1	Implement	Apr 2022	May 2022
1	Reflect	May 2022	May 2022
2	Plan	May 2022	May 2022
2	Implement	May 2022	May 2022
2	Reflect	May 2022	May 2022

Thematic Model

The research uses a thematic model that focuses on qualitative measures and covers the first cycle involving the three core activities of planning, action, and fact-finding. The secondary research involved the use of academic literature and theory

The Study's Limitations

Because many databases providing important information required a membership fee, the researcher was limited to accessing either publicly accessible databases or databases to which the university paid. This has the potential to jeopardize the accuracy and integrity of the data used in this research.

Fuel Theft Model

Fuel theft from fuel tanks is another significant concern that exists all over the globe. Fuel theft is malpractice involving fuel stolen from fuel tanks when the vehicle owner is there. The vehicle owner is unaware of fuel theft and will become aware of fuel theft when he drives the vehicle the following time. However, the vehicle's owner may encounter several difficulties due to fuel theft. A digital fuel gauge should be installed in the vehicle to prevent such an issue. Because the Digital Fuel Meter in that single board computer is used, it can send a notification to the owner of the vehicle when fuel is stolen using sensors and API integration with the smartphone application. Because this process takes place in real-time, it is more accurate and secure. The Vehicle Fuel Theft Detection System with smartphone notification has applications in automobiles, motorcycles, and other transportation and fuel-consuming industries. This project includes a single board computer that sends notifications to the vehicle owner when fuel theft occurs. One of the primary worries for many bikers and automobile owners is the theft of their gas tanks. Fuel from motorcycles and automobiles has been taken on several occasions. Some of us

have even experienced this firsthand. The primary goal of this effort is to prevent a scenario like this.

When developing the smartphone app-based fuel theft detection system, we employed a quantity sensor to measure the fuel level in the petrol tank. If the level falls below a threshold level, the sensor sends a specific signal to the microcontroller, which is subsequently processed. The single board computer then activates the trigger and sends a notification to the vehicle's or bike's owner. The microcontroller, often known as the Central Processing Unit (CPU), is the system's beating heart. In this situation, the amount of fuel or diesel will fall, which will cause the microcontroller to be activated through the level sensor. We have taken a signal from the ignition key to prevent this problem. When the bike owner, vehicle owner, or driver puts the key into the ignition lock and turns the key on, a signal is sent to the microcontroller, which controls the bike or automobile. The microcontroller will recognize that the bike or automobile has been started in this manner, and it will cease monitoring the fuel level. With this project, we have included an ignition key for the bike. The level sensor is activated only when the key is withdrawn from the ignition lock, and the ignition switch is depressed. The system will be engaged whenever the individual gets out of the automobile and takes the key out of his or her possession.

Our Project approach is dependent on hardware and software. It includes a single board computer, Ultra Sonic Sensor, Four Ethanol Emission Sensors, 4 Analog to Digital Converters and an integrated smart phone application for the layman user.

Fig.1 Proposed Model

The simple proposed VFTD model is revealed in Figure 1. Here we have attached our two sensors HCSR04 ultrasonic Sensor and MQ Ethanol Emission Sensor to our fuel tank which uses its functionality to determine the distance of previous fuel in the tank and then entered fuel value. Simultaneously, MQ gives the purity check. Our Single board Computer, Raspberry Pi Board receives the readings and performs the calculations to give statistics to our database and database provides those Statistics to the application.

A. Fuel value extraction

The most general theft made by the fuel suppliers, is by showing tempered readings. It means when consumer ask for certain quantity of fuel to be filled, they temper the readings and give less what we asked for. In this way, the consumer doesn't get what they paid for.

In our proposed system, we cater this problem by providing an effective solution. So that consumer cannot be fooled and robbed. By integrating this system, the consumer will be able to keep track of the fuel in his vehicle fuel tank. It will show the readings of current fuel level in the tank and new fuel value after refilling it.

For this purpose, we have suggested the HC SR04 Ultrasonic Sensor. This sensor is a 4-pin module, whose pin names are Vcc, Trigger, Echo and Ground respectively. The module has two eyes like projects in the front which forms the Ultrasonic transmitter and Receiver. The Ultrasonic transmitter transmits an ultrasonic wave, this wave travels in air and when it gets objected by any material it gets reflected back toward the sensor this reflected wave is observed by the Ultrasonic receiver module. The sensor works with the simple formula i-e:

$$\textit{Distance} = \textit{Speed} \times \textit{Time}$$

Now with the help of this sensor, we can calculate the fuel level using the above formulae. The circuitry inbuilt on the module will calculate the time taken for the US wave to come back from the hit fuel-level and turns on the echo pin high for that same particular amount of time. Now the total time of wave travel can be converted into distance by using the simple formula i-e:

$$\textit{Total Capacity of Fuel Tank} - (\textit{Wave Time} \times 0.000148)$$

The same formula will be used for calculating the distance of previous fuel level in the tank and similarly for the new fuel level after refilling. From these values, we can easily determine the theft by simply taking the difference of two values.

B. Purity extraction

The other theft made at consumer end is providing low quality fuel while refilling at fuel stations. This leads to frequent engine servicing of vehicles and more fuel consumption. Hence, the consumer suffers by paying more and compromising the quality of the engine.

In our project we have worked with ethanol fuel i-e E85 Fuel flex. E85 is an abbreviation typically referring to an ethanol fuel blend of 85% ethanol fuel and 15% fuel or other hydrocarbon by volume. The allowable ethanol content in E85 ranges from 51% to 83%.

For purity check, we are using four MQ- Ethanol Emission Sensors which will check the concentration, purity and emission of ethanol fuel entered in the vehicle fuel tank. We have built the circuit on four sensors to achieve the most accurate reading of ethanol and moreover to avoid any kind of casualties. Each sensor has been assigned the weightage of 25% hence getting purity check out of 100%.

This percentage can be achieved with the simple formula of aggregation.

$$\frac{\textit{Sum of values from each sensor}}{\textit{Total No. of sensors}} \times 100$$

The calculated percentage will show the quality of ethanol. And consumer will be able to determine the purity of the fuel intake at real-time.

C. Application Wireframes

Fig. A1

Fig. A2

Fig. A3

Fig. A4

The Application would be user friendly with limited controls and can easily be installed into the present car infotainment systems which compromises of:

- Launch screen - *figure. A1*
- Login screen - *figure. A2*
- Home Screen - *figure. A3*
- Vehicle information screen - *figure. A4*

Analysis

A Fuel System is frequently used to keep up with oversight, make due, and screen fuel utilization in any association, including transportation, like rail, street, air, or water. Rather than manual perception, organizations today defy a critical hindrance in fuel transportation. This manual perception is an expensive procedure for planning and assessing the fuel's actual working, and it might bring about monetary misfortunes for the organization. Most organizations have no work or evaluating cycles to ensure that the quantity of liters on the bill of offer matches the aggregate sum of ready gas. The vehicle proprietor drives the car to the corner store, fills the tank, and acquires a report from the siphon supervisor enumerating the number of liters of fuel infused into the tank, the date, and the number. The main impetus conveys this receipt to the organization's proprietor, who keeps track of it and gives the absolute to the siphon proprietor toward the finish of every month. This situation is tormented with imperfections: the driver has no thought whether how much gas infused amid the fuel rises to the sum demonstrated on the receipt. Another imperfection in the methodology is the siphon station chief's deceptive mind.

As indicated by the hypothetical outcomes, most purchasers experience issues physically observing and measuring their fuel use. Thus, a gadget should be able to examine and measure fuel use productively, diminishing the executive's concerns. Even though such gadgets are available, they are exorbitant, and organizations should exclude them in their spending plans while investigating fuel use and the pertinence of those systems overall. The proposed System depends on the current innovation and minimal expense of electronic parts, making it fitting for any business or exchange that depends on cars as an essential asset. As a basic asset for an organization, Mobility would help the organization's main concern. It is basic to deal with how much fuel is used by the accessible asset. The manual recognition is utilized in associations with a month-to-month concurrence with Petrol/Diesel suppliers. Manual recognition frequently costs the firm

extra since the voucher is created with the erroneous amount of fuel liters. An incorporated robotized framework is proposed for this situation since it will consider machine-controlled fuel checking and examination. A Fuels System is frequently used to monitor oversight, make due, and screen fuel utilization in any transportation association, like rail, street, air, or water. Rather than manual perception, organizations today face a critical hindrance in fuel transportation. This manual perception is an expensive procedure for planning and assessing the fuel's actual working, and it might bring about monetary misfortunes for the organization. Most organizations have no work or reviewing cycles to ensure that the quantity of liters on the bill of offer matches the aggregate sum of gas ready. The vehicle proprietor drives the car to the service station, fills the tank, and acquires a report from the siphon administrator itemizing the number of liters of fuel infused into the tank, the date, and the number. The main thrust conveys this receipt to the organization's proprietor, who keeps track of it and gives it all out to the siphon proprietor toward the finish of every month. This situation is tormented with defects: the driver has no thought whether how much gas infused amid the fuel approaches the sum demonstrated on the receipt. Another imperfection in the methodology is the siphon station chief's untrustworthy astuteness. A perfect representation is the presence of corporate representatives who submit burglary by computing the amount of gas input. Numerous organizations ought to consider every one of the variables referenced above, requiring an incorporated computerized gadget that tests the gas spent and distinguishes fuel misrepresentation, saving the corporate a lot of cash. Moreover, this innovation gives a minimal expense answer for the following transportation to distinguish big fuel haulers, as code information in gas archives are kept on the end clients' workstations or cell phones. The experience includes a few fuel thefts as the big hauler amount changes many times before showing up at the objective and a few liters of petroleum at the hour of commencement. Carbon is conveyed to areas by different means,

including allowed street tanks, fundamental boats, railways, and pipelines. This Method centers just around controlling street gas big haulers utilized for fuel conveyance. The Method offers the complete procedure accessible available for deciding how much |what rate |what amount of fuel is presented, and the amount of the activity is lost. This defends our properties by guaranteeing total fuel straightforwardness, all-out compromise, and insurance against fuel burglary. The whole framework gives a financially savvy energy control framework that is both costly and controlled, explicitly intended for Asian organizations that consider fuel burglary a huge impediment yet can't pay, and for PCs as of now accessible available because of costly existing arrangements. Observing is a finished resource recuperation instrument that can screen, make due, and recover vehicles. We can oversee and record resources more proficiently and assume we track them, saving time and energy. Utilizing GPS Fleet's following information, we will gauge proficiency and put a cost cap on future costs. This expands the association's estimate by raising the amount of administration given, bringing about expanded income and client devotion. The above programmed Fleet Following Reports is basic diagrams that help the United States of America distinguish functional issues and work on armada the executives. The Autonomous Fuel Monitoring System comprises fundamental electrical parts mounted on significant street big haulers to screen activity and volume. When placed into the tank, it estimates the quantity of gas liters, and after the fuel is taken or spilled, it gives the assessed information to be audited. In this examination, a partner in consideration talks about the obstructions related to fuel control frameworks and how to tackle these difficulties using a robotized electronic gadget. The article talks about issues with the equipment and programming of a gadget that needs the activity of gas liters through an excess association and causing they are processed by GSM to the chairman's telephone cell phone yet remotely on the compact machine.

Fuel Management Systems are utilized to make due, direct, and screen fuel use in any kind of organization that utilizes transportation as a strategy for trade, including rail, street, air, and water. Because of manual observing, endeavors are presently faced with extreme trouble controlling fuel transportation. This manual checking is wasteful in computing and surveying fuel use and could bring about monetary misfortunes for the firm. There is no recording or examining framework in the typical situation utilized by most firms to guarantee that the quantity of liters expressed on the receipt compares to the genuine amount of fuel in the tank. The driver drives to the fuel terminal, fills the tank, and gets a receipt from the siphon director that incorporates the number of liters of gas filled in the vehicle tank, the date, and the sum. The driver presents this receipt to the association's chief, who holds the record and moves the cash to the siphon proprietor toward the month's end. The present circumstance is hampered by various likely blames, including the driver's failure to decide whether the amount of petroleum put in the fuel is equivalent to the sum demonstrated on the receipt. One more weakness in the framework is the siphon station supervisor's making of misleading data. A third model is the cooperation of firm administration individuals who lead extortion by distorting data about the amount of fuel presented. Numerous organizations should think about all of the previously mentioned contemplations, requiring the need for a robotized gadgets framework that examines the gas ingested as well as explores fuel burglary to save the association from misfortune. Moreover, this Method considers the proficient checking of vehicles to pinpoint the fuel area. Big haulers and a product information base for fuel records are put away on end-client workstations or cell phones. The information base stores the number of gas liters right now and the number of fuel robberies that happen when the limit of the big hauler shifts fundamentally before showing up at the objective. Fuel transportation or supply to the areas is achieved through various techniques, including authorized thruway tanks, huge

boats, rail lines, and pipelines. In the area of the executives, this framework exclusively centers around thruway gas tanks for fuel conveyance. The System is the most over-the-top total arrangement available, for it is placed and squandered to decide how much gas. This safeguards our resources by giving thorough fuel liability, whole compromise, and assurance against fuel robbery. This framework gives a productive, practical, and mechanized fuel the board framework that is explicitly customized for Kuwaiti associations who consider fuel robbery to be a serious issue however track down it is difficult to manage the cost of the frameworks as of now available inferable from the significant expense of existing arrangements. Hypothetical examinations uncover that 90% of people experience issues managing and surveying fuel use by manual checking. Subsequently, there is a requirement for a framework that can lessen fuel the executive's worries while simultaneously breaking down and computing fuel use mechanically. Albeit such frameworks are open, they are expensive; along these lines, partnerships don't think about putting resources into them in the wake of contrasting fuel use and the value of such frameworks. The proposed framework is fabricated utilizing promptly available and modest electrical parts, making it valuable for any organization or business that depends on autos as a crucial asset. GPS Fleet Tracking is an across-the-board administration framework for observing, making due, and recuperating resources. We can more readily oversee and screen assets' areas by observing them, decreasing sat around and fuel use. We can break down execution and limit consumption by utilizing GPS Fleet Tracking information. This builds the firm's worth by improving the nature of administration, bringing about expanded income and client satisfaction. These mechanized Fleet Tracking reports are straightforward diagrams that assist us with finding functional issues and upgrading armada the board. The Automatic Fuel Management System comprises fundamental electronic parts placed on roadway big haulers to gauge and check the degree of fuel. It screens

the number of gas liters when put into the tank and when fuel is taken or spilled, and afterward communicates that information for examination and additional data. By checking your assets, you can all the more likely oversee and screen their areas, diminishing sat around and fuel. Fuel estimation information is basic in different water-related ventures. Computerized water estimating framework is expected to avoid the difficulties related to manual estimation. The location of fake action and anomalies in vehicle development are two significant difficulties for the vehicle armada business. Fuel robbery, stacking and dumping-related cheats, course deviations, insufficient fuel support, and successive disappointments are a portion of these that make huge costs to the association.

Discussion

Fuel drive-offs occur when people fill their cars with fuel at a gas station and then drive away without paying. Many of the gas stations are deserted, with no one fueling automobiles. As is customary, customers at gas stations must exit their vehicles, fill up with petrol, pay the bill, and then drive away. For example, in Kuwait, driving away without paying has increased significantly in recent years. According to The Age, Kuwait's major daily, every gas station loses roughly \$100,000 yearly. The total is estimated to be over 20 million. Some may claim that video monitoring is already in place to prevent such things from occurring to manage the theft issue. However, in certain nations, stealing fuel is no longer regarded as a criminal but rather a civil problem in which the owner is responsible for recovering the money. The proprietor is liable for carrying the criminal to court and recuperating the cash after the preliminary. Accordingly, video checking is inadequate in shutting down these activities. Gas station robbery has encouraged a dire interest in an innovation that can help forestall burglary. We investigated using cell phones to oversee robbery worries to foster that technique. Each gadget has an actual alternate location known as a MAC address. Before starting the request, we examined a few troubles. Moral

strategies for gaining the client's MAC address and plate number and keeping the technique up to current with changing mechanical and environmental elements are additionally viewed as basic issues. Gathering information from cell phones, for example, MAC addresses, could increment moral clash and abuse human security. Although MAC discovery might be significant in keeping away from robbery, it probably won't be difficult to do so morally by getting customer approval. Therefore, finding an answer for this issue before continuing with this study is indispensable. The structure may assemble the client's gadget MAC addresses as a precaution measure to lessen fuel burglary. This structure might prevent guilty parties from perpetrating wrongdoings by explicitly recording the MAC Address of guilty parties' cell phones/gadgets and informing the client that their cell phone MAC Address has been recorded as a hindrance to driving off. Identifying MAC addresses alone can't be utilized to separate fraudsters and real clients. It should be upheld with precise and steady information that can be considered and an emotionally supportive network that utilizes business insight and AI calculations to decide potential robberies. Thus, this study plan joined large information investigation and business knowledge with MAC discovery. The crucial goal is to decide the equipment and programming important to construct a gadget equipped for identifying MAC addresses. The goal is to gather client data to assist with coordinating it with the recognized MAC locations and show the client's name to welcome them. Since they have been perceived, forthcoming burglars will become mindful and may pay or pick to drive away without fueling. In this situation, simply distinguishing the MAC address is lacking. We need a dynamic instrument that can help us in deciding whether someone, in particular, is a criminal or a genuine customer. Enormous information investigation might support breaking down continuous information delivered in an assortment of strategies, including distinguished MAC locations and client data from the client's data set. The reality and build a framework to support perceiving the

MAC locations of shoppers heading out to corner stores to renew their vehicles by showing their names, assuming they are a client with the fuel station. Their data may be taken from the clients' enrolled information base and displayed on a screen to cause them to feel invited and perceived. Moreover, present an advancement rebate show invite message tempting unregistered clients to enroll with our framework. Numerous specialists advance the protection methodology for data security. For instance, the proposed framework that forestalls faked traffic is the framework equipped for identifying, responding quickly and exactly, and recognizing genuine and satirizing traffic. The genuineness part alone is lacking to avoid misrepresentation attacks; it should likewise address morals, honesty, and anticipation, and chance administration strategy is the best extortion approach. The best degrees of safeguard appraisal and confirmation with work detachment and correspondence control all guide the advancement of the affirmation framework. At last, there is an emphasis on the meaning of embracing avoidance and impediment to hold clients back from becoming survivors of misrepresentation. Notwithstanding counteraction, the existing writing study recommends that the utilization of identification as a methodology is likewise proposed as the significant component in any proposed security framework. In our framework, we focused on identifying the MAC address of cell phones. For instance, various retail shopping centers have utilized MAC address distinguishing proof of gadgets using Wi-Fi to recognize the number of buyers present at a specific second in air terminals or retail outlets, which has prompted the shopping centers to plan their promoting strategies around the got information. It has planned contraptions to accumulate information from iPhone and Android cell phones appended to vehicles to ascertain the number of vehicles going through a specific course to survey traffic. A few methodologies can distinguish the client's MAC address, like a looter's MAP. This approach is utilized at MIT, where free WIFI is given to understudies, and understudies are allowed to involve

with this help however much they like. Burglar's MAP is a framework strategy used to screen and envision the development of understudies on the MIT grounds. Burglar's MAP can, without much stretch, decide the MAC address of gadgets with a WIFI administration card coordinated. One more recognition framework, BLUEID, laid out the procedure of recognizing client gadget information, for example, a gadget's MAC address or an IMEI number. This framework might imitate a gadget's Bluetooth personality so the client can associate through it, and when associated, each of the client's gadget's information can be just gotten too. The methodology for finding the MAC address of a cell phone client depends on solid presence location utilizing aloof administration outline sniffing. This approach is utilized for Macintosh location by communicating a test solicitation to all passageways, and from those passages, the gadget's data might be promptly recognized or recorded. BMS is the term given by the scientist to a scanner that can quickly recognize the MAC-ID of gadgets. The essential capacity of this scanner is to identify the MAC-ID of gadgets associated with discoverable Bluetooth gadgets. Since many people's gadgets are currently associated with the vehicle BT framework for music tuning in, this scanner can get the signs of vehicle Bluetooth and separate the subtleties of the client's MAC-ID.

Entrepreneurial Competencies

This project has been difficult and time-consuming for a variety of reasons. The study was conducted during a very frantic time for the author since she had just acquired leadership of a new fuel theft software. It took both time and money to do this. This financial commitment, along with the requirements of doing research, was both satisfying and stressful.

To keep the fuel theft software running, it was essential to move banks, automobiles, and internet and phone providers, all of which created distinct challenges. Though insignificant, these activities sometimes require lengthy travel to the offices of many service providers. Managing the human factors, such as learning about and integrating new personnel, was the most difficult aspect

of this project. Poor processes and procedures, a lack of oversight, and a lack of motivation all led to the decision to make the required changes.

It is difficult to gain workers' confidence while drawing their attention to these issues. Attempting to remove oneself from the activity to capture and comprehend meaning adds another degree of complexity. But now that we've completed the study and made some improvements to the fuel theft program, we can say it was well worth it.

Despite overcoming the challenges above, the author openly admits that several aspects of the study might be done differently if given the opportunity. Before making any changes, more time would be spent learning about the fuel theft app, how it functions, the staff, and their unique needs and desires. Second, by not dictating particular procedures but rather defining the desired outcomes and letting employees choose the best approach to accomplish these objectives, more individuals would have an opportunity to influence the resulting modifications. This may have increased buy-in and commitment to the changes, but it may have required ongoing reinforcement and pushing.

Execution Strategy

While the author did create a vision and plan for the fuel theft app, the execution of that strategy may have been enhanced by identifying and growing the essential specialized entrepreneurial talents ahead of time. For example, the construction of a "competency plan" may have highlighted the need for increased attention to interpersonal interactions and an explanation of the reason for the adjustments. This may have led to a more productive practice in general. As a consequence of this study, the author recognizes the need to not just prepare ahead of time but also anticipate the knowledge, attitudes, and talents required to put those plans into action.

Even though the change was initially challenging, the author identified the issues that had hindered the process via introspective analysis. This introspection may provide two further insights. To begin, it is necessary to engage in critical and honest self-reflection to thoroughly understand the issues they encounter. When issues develop during the transition to the new state of things, it is critical to be adaptable enough to quickly change your plans and approach.

An Examination Of The Development Of Entrepreneurial Approach

According to Mitchelmore and Rowley (2009), an entrepreneurial approach is critical to the creation and success of anti-theft solutions. Even though Bartlett and Ghoshal (1997) divided abilities into three broad categories (Figure 16), these categories are still relatively wide. Furthermore, a company owner must decide not just the long-term goal but also the abilities required to carry it out effectively. According to the Literature Review Section, the goal of doing this study was to contribute to the current body of knowledge by delineating the competence required to resuscitate an ailing small or medium-sized firm (SME).

Fig entrepreneurial competencies

While no comprehensive list of entrepreneurial abilities has been produced, the author did get some insight throughout the study process via introspection and analysis. Despite the design of a strategy to improve the operations function via adopting systems and processes centered on utilizing KM inside the fuel theft app, the change process was unsuccessful during the first Cycle. After understanding the challenges the change process faced with RTC via critical reflection, the author made improvements to the process and began following the stages specified in Kotter's change model in Cycle 2. As a result, in addition to the personal lessons learned, this study has added to the literature by supporting the use of change models when implementing change. What Happens Next: Moving Entrepreneurship Forward in Our Lives and Organizations As previously stated, the author's leadership was judged insufficient after careful consideration. A PDP has been developed to solve these issues (Appendix F). The author thinks that lifelong education is crucial for personal and professional success. That is why it is critical to figure out how to document the

study results so they may be utilized later. As a result, the author feels the proposals are critical to future success, both personally and institutionally. These are discussed below: Analytical Thinking

The capacity to critically review one's work is a vital skill that, although refined for this study, might be used in other circumstances and by the fuel theft app. If you're going to engage in some critical thinking, you should think about not just your talents but also the ones your organization needs to grow. The organization should seek to nurture or attract them if they do not already exist.

Sharpen Your Strategic Thinking Skills Strategic thinking may help decision-making in one's personal and professional life, making it a vital and effective tool for any entrepreneur. Strategy formulation is critical for firms because it sets the path to future success.

As a consequence of his strategic decisions during this study, the author finds that he has to concentrate on developing his strategic thinking. Take Notice of What Others Are Saying the study's results highlight the need for open lines of communication to guarantee the success of the change implementation process. Following critical reflection, the author identified a need for improvement in communication skills, which was subsequently included in the personal development plan (PDP). Maintain Your Flexibility Because of the author's adaptability throughout the study process; the author modified the change process to conform to a more systematic model. No amount of strategic planning or consideration will be fruitful if the ability to adapt to unforeseen adjustments in strategic demands or prospects is lost.

Conclusion

Today, fuel is a non-renewable energy source on the planet, making it a valuable commodity for civilization. Fuel theft and other fuel-related issues are causing havoc in industries that rely on it. The world of fuel has a huge issue with fuel theft, and they don't have a major answer or parameter to manage it. We are working on a Fuel theft Alert and Fuel Monitoring System project. The project primarily monitors the fuel in the tank via GPS monitoring of the tank,

RFID verification of the person aboard the vehicle, and a panic button in the fuel tank. The tank comprises temperature, pressure, and fuel level sensors. Each of the three sensors has a distinct attribute that aids in collecting tank data. The temperature sensor provides the temperature of the tank, while the pressure sensor informs us about the pressure of the tank, and the level sensor is the sensor that tells us about the amount of fuel within the tank.

All of the data is collectively saved to the cloud. The alert and data are sent to the data center to measure all of the parameters on the tank and calculate the data given for the safety and the industries to check the consumption and security of the fuel, as well as to maintain the log for the industries' annual budget. For a long time, fuel theft has been a significant source of worry for fleet operators and vehicle owners. The source of the problem was discovered, and several preventative measures were implemented. There have been other fuel-tracking systems in the past. Still, none were effective enough to supply them with specific information about the exact amount of fuel taken and the exact position and time of the pilferage that may substantiate the allegation. The Fuel Monitoring system monitors the fuel level and volume in the truck fuel tank and the tanker compartments in real-time. It also includes a method for identifying theft or fraud situations in the event of fuel theft or leakage.

Furthermore, the system can monitor the whereabouts of each fuel-carrying tanker to pinpoint the site of any incident that may have happened. This technology automatically checks fuel quality, recognizing fuel contamination with water or additives. IoT-based sensors affixed to the tanker's surface distinguish fuel kinds based on a specified pattern and perform automated corrections. It continually detects tank fill-up and fuel draining volumes by accurately monitoring fuel volume. The data is transferred to a cloud-based server through the IoT gateway linked to the vehicle, which is monitored in the KPI dashboard. Any change in oil volume is recorded as sensory

data and sent as an alarm to a cloud-based application. The GPS tracker locates the vehicle in real-time and monitors the position of fuel replenishing and emptying. When the fuel monitoring system is integrated with the analytics software, reports on all fuel fillers and potential fuel thefts are generated, complete with accurate date, time, position and map markers, beginning and final fuel levels, and fillings/thefts volume information. Using this sophisticated data, fleet owners can often reduce fuel theft in their fleets by 90%.

Geofences may regulate unit activity inside specific zones or, conversely, outside of them. When a unit arrives, departs, or pauses at a certain Geofences, notifications may be issued. You will be notified if the Fuel sensor placed in a unit is unplugged. It might have occurred due to a wiring problem or an intended disconnect. When a speed limit infringement occurs, an alert is generated. The speed limit is determined by the mechanism for assessing the speeding set in the unit's parameters. The sophisticated fuel sensor monitors fuel quality automatically, allowing for optional additive or water mixing. When such an occurrence happens, an alert is generated. When a car is filled up, or a fuel drain happens, an alert is delivered. The alert comprises information such as when and where the incident occurred. In an emergency, the driver may use the panic button and issue an alarm. The notice includes the vehicle number, position, and time. The Fuel Monitoring System will offer fuel security, allowing fuel companies to be worry-free regarding fuel transportation and fuel theft. The sensors will collect records and aid in the accounting of the fuel businesses, and GPS tracking will monitor the fuel tank while it is being transported. For human verification, an RFID card is utilized, which helps to ensure that the correct individual makes the delivery. More sensors may be added to the monitoring system, increasing tanker safety. Web application information translation and representation. This application may be improved in the future. Improving system security against unwanted access is another outstanding challenge.

In our research, a general solution to deal with vehicle fuel theft is presented. We are providing an efficient and better alternative to deal with the fuel theft problem. In our proposed/designed system, the integrated application provides the statistical data of current fuel measures and real-time fuel-filling data with the help of the readings provided by the sensors. Moreover, the app will also indicate the purity of the fuel. Thus, in this way, users will be able to detect the theft in real-time, hence minimizing the fuel theft problem, which will, in return, play a major role in building consumer loyalty. Therefore, I would like to conclude this dissertation with the following quotation.

“We never stop investigating. We are never satisfied that we know enough to get by. Every question we answer leads on to another question. This has become the greatest survival trick of our species.” – Morris, Desmond

References

1. Manisha Rinayat, Ganesh Barde, Naina Tarpe, Aksahy Mohurle, Priyanka Gadewar and Suchita S. Kamble . “GSM Based Vehicle Fuel Monitoring and Theft Detection System with SMS Indication”- 2017
2. Ganesh Katkar, Shivam Lanke, Anand Kumar and Prof. Swati Khawate. “Fuel Checker and Theft Indication”- 2017
3. Mrs. Udayavalli.V and Mrs.M.Omameswari. “Embedded System Based Intelligent Digital Fuel Gauge”- 2014
4. Mr. Ravindra S. Lahane*, Mr. Nilesh Pawar, Swapnil Ghogardare. “Analysis and Design -Of Fuel Theft Prevention And Automation”- 2016
5. Shanmuganathan J and B.C.Kavitha. “Tracking and Theft Prevention System for Two Wheeler Using Android”- 2015
6. Manihatty Bojan, "Designing Vehicle Tracking System – An Open Source Approach", *IEEE International Conference on Vehicular Electronics and Safety (ICVES)*, pp. 135-140, 2014.
7. R. D. Kokate, "Fuel Monitoring and Vehicle Tracking", *International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT)*, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 166-169, 2012.
8. Jitendra Singh Tamang, "GSM Based Fuel Theft Detector Using Microcontroller", *International Journal of Advance Electrical and Electronics Engineering (IJEIT)*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 7-12, 2015.
9. Xiaoli Sun, "The intelligent crude oil anti-theft system based on IoT under different scenarios", *International Conference on Knowledge Based and Intelligent Information and Engineering Systems*, pp. 1581-1588, 2016.
10. KaleemHabib, ArifIqbal Umar, Noor UIAmeen, Muhammad Ali And ShoukatMehmood. “Anomaly Detection in Fuel Expense And Mileage Through Data Mining” - 2017
11. Prof. S. Raja, Dr. G. G. Geetha. “Detection of Fuel Theft in Heavy Vehicle” -2016
12. Authentix. “Stop Fuel Fraud”- 2013
13. KaleemHabib and ArifIqbal Umar. “Anomalies Calculation and Detection in Fuel Expense through Data Mining”- 2015
14. Mr.Senthilkumar.R, Ganapathi.M, Arunkumar.D, Goutham.G and Karthick.M. “Fuel Monitoring

15. System For Fuel Management”- 2017
16. Microtronics Technologies. “GSM based Vehicle Fuel Theft Detection System with SMS indication”-2015
17. SS Aher, RD Kokate, Fuel monitoring and vehicle tracking. Int. J. Eng. Innovat. Technol. 1(3), 166–169 (2012)
18. Huang, H., Xiao, S., Meng , X., and Xiong, Y., “A Remote Home Security System Based on Wireless Sensor Network and GSM Technology”, Proceedings of Second International Conference on Networks Security, Wireless Communications and Trusted Computing, 2010. (Conference Proceedings)
19. B.G. Nagaraja, Ravi Rayappa, M. Mahesh, Chandrasekhar M. Patil, Dr.T.C. Manjunath:- “Design & Development of a GSM Based Vehicle Theft Control System” 978-0-7695-3516-6/08 ©2008 IEEE, DOI 10.1109/ICACC.2009.154, pp.148-152.
20. LPC2131/32/34/36/38, Single-chip 16/32-bit microcontrollers; 32/ 64/ 128/256/512 kB ISP/IAP flash with 10- bit ADC and DAC. Rev. 5.1- 29 July 2011. [http:// www.nxp.com/documents /data sheet/LPC2131_32_34_36_38. pdf](http://www.nxp.com/documents/data_sheet/LPC2131_32_34_36_38.pdf).
21. SIM900, The GSM/GPRS module for M2M applications.[http://www.propox.com/download/docs/SIM900 .pdf](http://www.propox.com/download/docs/SIM900.pdf).
22. MAX232x EIA-232 Drivers / Receivers. SLLS047M– February 1989 – Revised November 2014 [http://www.ti.com/lit/ ds/symlink/max232.pdf](http://www.ti.com/lit/ds/symlink/max232.pdf)
23. MAX232 datasheet. [http://www. Engineersgarage.com/electronic-components/max232datasheet](http://www.Engineersgarage.com/electronic-components/max232datasheet).
24. D. Liu, Z. Liang, Y. Li, H. Yang, FITME, *Research and design of a high performance GPS vehicle monitoring system*, **Vol.3**, 59 – 62, (2010)
25. T. Enomoto, M. Sekine, S. Chikara, K. Kubota, Intelligent Transportation Systems, *A freight status management system with restriction to record loading/unloading information by location*, **Vol.3**, 548 – 553, (2003)
26. A. Tahat, A. Said, F. Jaouni, W. Qadamani, ISCE, *Android-based universal vehicle diagnostic and tracking system*, **Vol.16**, 137-143, (2012)
27. M. Saraswati, E. Kuantama, P. Mardjoko, Eur. Symp. Comp. Model. Sim., *Design and Construction of Water Level Measurement System Accessible through SMS*, **Vol. 6.**, 49-53, (2012)
28. Fleet Management Systems from [http://gpsintegrated.com/services/fleet-management- system](http://gpsintegrated.com/services/fleet-management-system)
29. M. Saraswati, E. Kuantama, P. Mardjoko, Eur. Symp. Comp. Model. Sim., *Design and*

Construction of Water Level Measurement System Accessible through SMS, **6**, 49-53, (2012)

30. M. Saravanan, S. Aishwarya, L. N. Aravindan, Sci & Inf. Conf., *Tracking anomalies in vehicle movements using mobile GIS*, (2013)
31. T. Le-Tien, V. Phung, The IEEE International Symp. on Es. Design, Test & Apps., *Routing and Tracking System for Mobile Vehicles in Large Area*, **5** 297- 300,(2010)
32. M. Popa, B. Suta, TELFOR, *A solution for tracking a fleet of vehicles*, **19**,1558 –1561, (2011)
33. Haldorai, A. Ramu, and S. Murugan, Social Aware Cognitive Radio Networks, Social Network Analytics for Contemporary Business Organizations, pp. 188–202. doi:10.4018/978-1-52255097-6.ch010
34. R. Arulmurugan and H. Anandakumar, Region-based seed point cell segmentation and detection for biomedical image analysis, International Journal of Biomedical Engineering and Technology, vol. **27**, no. 4, p. 273, 2018.
35. P .Chen, S. Liu , ICIE, *Intelligent Vehicle Monitoring System Based on GPS, GSM and GIS*, **4**, 38-40, (2010).
36. D. Liu, Z. Liang, Y. Li, H. Yang, FITME, *Research and design of a high performance GPS vehicle monitoring system*, **3**,59 – 62,(2010)
37. T. Enomoto, M. Sekine, S. Chikara, K. Kubota, Intelligent Transportation Systems, *A freight status management system with restriction to record loading/unloading information by location*, **3**, 548 – 553, (2003)
38. A. Tahat, A. Said, F. Jaouni, W. Qadamani, ISCE, *Android-based universal vehicle diagnostic and tracking system*, **16**, 137-143, (2012).
39. A. B. o. Statistics. (2018, 03 August). *3412.0 - Migration, Kuwait, 201415*. Available:<http://www.abs.gov.au/ausstats/abs@.nsf/Previousproducts/3412.0Main%2015?opendocument&tabname=Summary&prodno=3412.0&issue=20141&num=&view=>.
40. T. Age. (2017, 03 August). *'It's time to be tough': Coalition vows crackdown on \$20m fuel theft epidemic*. Available: <https://www.theage.com.au/national/victoria/its-time-to-be-tough-coalitionvows-crackdown-on-20m-fuel-theft-epidemic-20170801-gxmxy6.html>.

41. Ben-Hagemann. (2017, 03 August). *Victorian initiative to criminalise petrol theft*. Available: <https://www.c-store.com.au/2017/08/01/initiativecriminalise-petrol-theft/>
42. P. L. Jordan and A. J. Sellers, "Reliable Presence Detection through Passive IEEE 802.11 Management Frame Sniffing," *Military Cyber Affairs*, vol. 1, p. 5, 2015.
43. S. Malliga and A. Tamilarasi, "Collaborative Framework for Detection, Prevention, and Traceback of Flooding Attacks Using Marking and Filtering," *Information Security Journal: A Global Perspective*, vol. 18, pp. 74-86, 2009.
44. S. S. Halbouni, N. Obeid, and A. Garbou, "Corporate governance and information technology in fraud prevention and detection: Evidence from the UAE," *Managerial Auditing Journal*, vol. 31, pp. 589-628, 2016.
45. K. W. Kongsgard, N. A. Nordbotten, F. Mancini, R. Haakseth, and P. E. Engelstad, "Data Leakage Prevention for Secure Cross-Domain Information Exchange," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 55, pp. 37-43, 2017.
46. T. B. Agency, "Improving security," *Managerial Auditing Journal*, vol. 10, pp. 42-48, 1995.
47. S. Haigh, "Tracking people via WiFi (even when not connected)," vol. 2018, ed, 2015.
48. libelium. (2018, 30-September). *Smartphone Detection*, " *Libelium Connecting Sensors to the Cloud RSS*. Available: <http://www.libelium.com/products/meshlium/smartphone-detection/>
49. J. Huang, W. Albazraqoe, and G. Xing, "Blueid: A practical system for bluetooth device identification," in *INFOCOM, 2014 Proceedings IEEE*, 2014, pp. 2849-2857.